

MOOD AND MINDSETS IN THE CONTEMPORARY PROSUMPTION CULTURE

COLLABORATION AND SHARING IN CULINARY ACTIVITIES, DIGITAL IMPLICATIONS AND NEW DESIGN DIRECTIONS

Androulaki Maria
University of Edinburgh
mandroulaki@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Prosumerism and prosumption culture seems to be more and more apparent in everyday activities both in physical and digital world. This paper focuses on the importance of sharing and collaboration within prosumerism activities as well as on the importance of the unexpected.

In this paper the results of two studies on culinary activities of everyday life are critically presented. Our findings support the view that collaboration and sharing practices can play a significant role in activities of prosumerism. As it was found collaboration within prosumerism activities makes a substantial shift on the acquainted qualities and immaterial values of the end product. Furthermore the study shows that collaboration and sharing within prosumption promotes a mood shifting too. It is also suggested that an unexpected situation within collaborative prosumption activities contributes to the creation of new collaboration customs, establishes new ideas about the final product and draws further connections.

Keywords: prosumption, collaboration, the unexpected, culinary activities, mindsets

INTRODUCTION

Could culinary activities offer us a different insight in our consumer practices and indicate new design directions?

IS CONSUMPTION OUT OF CONTROL?

No doubt today our connection to the world through consumption culture is undergoing a transformation. It is evident that consumption and production are

changing. (Cambel 2005, Sopper 2009, Sasatelli 2007)

Kate Soper is talking about how the ethics and the politics of consumer's choice are changing. Soper critically refers to a new society shaped around happiness and desire, a field that is now actively re-shaped and re-evaluated and offers both a challenge and a chance for our society to re-evaluate consuming culture and to establish new culture practices for a better and more prosperous future.

PROSUMERISM AND DIGITAL PROSUMERISM

It is evident that consumers are adopting active roles in territories that were not long ago merely orientated through the market. It is a fact that today we are facing an époque where prosumerism i.e. the fusion of production and consumption as expressed by Toffler in his book 'The third wave' is becoming more and more evident and is starting to cover many areas that it didn't before. Prosumerism is still an active process in many fields and it is beginning to become apparent in many activities and ethos of today (DIY activities, self help groups, activism in consumerism etc). (Chunyan, Xie, 2007,)

In the digital domain the phenomenon of prosumerism is enlarged; prosumers are increasing in number more and more. Digital prosumers, on net communities and digital spaces create themselves digital content, share it, reuse it and change it.

COLLABORATIVE CONSUMPTION

A new form of consumption that is very evident in the digital domain today is collaborative consumption. (Rachel Botsman, 2010) The term collaborative

consumption describes an economic model based on sharing, swapping, bartering, trading or renting access to products, as opposed to the concept of ownership. Rachel Botsman in her book *'What is mine is Yours'* explains that collaborative consumption describes the rapid explosion in traditional sharing, bartering, lending, trading, renting, gifting, and swapping through network technologies on a scale and in ways never possible before.

According to Rachel Botsman through collaborative consumption there is an opportunity to consume "smarter" by moving away from the outdated concept of outright ownership that include not just consumables, but also our "time and space". Botsman highlights the importance and the contribution of immaterial values like trust, time and also space, to the new ways of collaborative consumption through net systems.

On the same direction within activities of prosumption, our research's findings suggest that collaboration within prosuming activities enhances immaterial values and changes the appreciation of the final product.

COLLABORATION, SHARING AND THE UNEXPECTED INVOLVED IN CULINARY ACTIVITIES OF PROSUMERISM.

Moisio, Arnould and Price (2004) claim that culinary activities have never lost the characteristics of prosumerism. Food meanings and practices embody social structures and relationships (Moisio, Arnould and Price, 2004). Culinary practices fluctuate with local economic and social contexts (Fischler, 1980). The aromas of the freshly cooked meals, the sounds of the cutlery, chats, the radio is on and an extra plate is on the table. The extra plate on the table is for the unexpected guest. In Greece this custom is still vivid in many areas and welcomes the unexpected in the hearth of the home. Unexpected situations, unexpected guests, the unexpected use of places, the unexpected use of ingredients in traditional recipes, and the unexpected use of local products, structure new conditions and form new situations.

IMMATERIAL VALUES, FOOD AND ATMOSPHERES

Mindsets and environments blend and create moods and tendencies and personal and or social atmospheres. Social space folds into mental space, into diaphanous concepts of spatiality which all too often take us away from materialized social realities.

The power of food to influence mood, to create different scenes, atmospheres, routines and special occasions is widely recognized from Plato to contemporary researchers and philosophers. In this paper attention will be focused more specifically into the power of the collaboration and sharing that is involved within culinary activities and the way it influences our mood, mindset and our perception of the final product.

THE STUDIES

Twenty five in depth interviews and an intervention, both related to prosumerism in culinary activities were carried out. These studies are part of a PhD research in the University of Edinburgh within the area of prosumption, digital media and architecture.

1. THE INTERVIEWS

The interviews contemplated prosumerism in culinary activities and unfold topics related to culinary activities as a social act, as a personal activity, culinary activities and well-being, culinary activities and therapeutic conditions, and culinary activities and leisure. Quotes from the interviews are presented below. The quotes are related mainly to sharing and co-consumption of food, and the way that co-consumption and sharing could affect our moods and mindsets.

The beneficial food co-consumption and food sharing

Although I don't eat much, there is always a problem with that, but if I am sitting around... when I am with good friends, and I do feel comfortable, my appetite will change and I will certainly eat more. I will make me feel not full and continue. It makes me feel good. I strongly believe that it is better when you share. With friends and people that you love you know, than eating on your own.

Food sharing, comforts or magnifies the threat of food consumption

"In big celebrations I don't usually find the food that I like to have.. So I find these occasions somehow uncomfortable also. I used to do long distance running and I used to be very disciplined on my food. Whereas with less people It's more likely for me to relax and actually enjoy."

Co-producing, cooking and negotiations

"Well yes, because it is not all about cooking, but with socializing too. What I like when I cook with my flat mates is that they propose also things and I also learn from them about recipes, it does not mean that I necessarily like it but I also see different ways of doing things and sometimes I also adopt their habits. And when I am cooking I talk a lot about their influence, saying this is something Elsa would do or ... Well yes we always had issues about how to cook things. Because we did have different habits of how ... Well we had to negotiate. a lot... how much oil, or what ingredients in particular and all that."

The unexpected, the surprise

"I would always also change and try new things if I can and actually it surprises my friends because they are used to something very traditional where I try something very different based on traditional recipes." An example (not what I have done) of what I might do to something, to represent what I have done before, is to take a Bounty bar, I would actually mix strawberry with coconut so when you have it, it is coconut with a strawberry taste and it shocks people, they think that it is something different."

Immaterial values and culinary activities

"Well even when I am buying products..., an example is Wheetabix... the cereals... and that is definitely the influence of my second flat mate L. because we had that for breakfast and then I sort of adopted it, because I never had cereals for breakfast before that. So that was L's influence in my breakfast eating habits."

Do you like recalling it? Is it like a memoir for you?

"E, yes it is! Yes yes, yes (smiling nicely and a lot)... yes it is like sharing the flat with L. again"

And on the net?

"Well I can imagine. . . because you cannot really smell it... on the net I would try to make an image... to have a picture of it on my mind."

'It is better in general when you cook with someone else, when you have somebody around. For example when my flat mates are around it is better because the time flies by.'

'I think that it worked really nice and it was fine because when you cook alone it is boring but when you cook with someone else it is better.'

The quotes from the interviews highlight the significance of the collaboration within prosuming culinary activities. The alteration of the mindset while cooking with collaboration and the different perspective of the final product. Even the feeling of collaboration, to feel like as if someone would collaborate, incorporates immaterial values to the process and shifts the understanding and the appreciation of the final product.

Supports of these findings were found in the intervention that is presented bellow

2. THE INTERVENTION COCKTAIL PARTICIPATION DIY CULINARY ACTIVITIES AND DIGITAL REFLECTIONS

Figure2. The recipes of the Cocktails

The intervention cocktail participation was an intervention created by the Architect's Association of Chania and it was both inspired and dedicated to the festivals that take place in public spaces. In fact, this intervention was created in order to close the conference-soiree "The activation of Public Spaces- Celebrating Public Space" that took place at the Center of Mediterranean Architecture at 02-10-2011. During the intervention the citizens participated in a

DIY culinary activity, in a public space. Within the intervention the unexpected was highlighted in two different ways. Firstly the unexpected transformation of a public space with ephemeral stands, to a market place and secondly the use of local traditional products in unexpected ways. At the intervention the participants were given the recipes and the ingredients for three cocktails. So, they had a try of making their own drink. The ingredients of the cocktails were a mixture of both traditional local products and the usual key ingredients of the cocktails.

During the intervention the participants had the opportunity to vote for their best cocktail and participate in a survey. The intervention was accompanied by a facebook event page where visitors followed the documentation of the event, they could vote for their favorite cocktail and leave their comments. In the question of the survey if they did the cocktail by themselves or if they took one already made 80% of the participants answered that they did it by themselves.

The comments of the participants during the intervention

Participant A:

I really enjoyed the event. I usually don't drink but I enjoyed the process a lot and now I know some very nice recipes. I followed the steps from the recipes and I asked for further explanations from the people at the bar. I will make them at home too. I am going for my third now.

Participant B:

Why trying my usual cocktail? I had the opportunity to learn how to do different ones!

Participant C:

Relaxed, not right or wrong, fun, nice result, doing something with friends

The comments of the Fb event page friends commenting on the recipes of the cocktail

Friend A:

If you add in that, and good company the success is

guaranteed!

Friend B:

Oh my God, how am I going to follow all these steps?

Friend C:

You are studying I see.

Figure 2. cocktail partYicipation

For the vote of the best cocktail at the night of the event the three cocktails where almost equally voted. On the Fb page of the event on the other hand the differences on the votes were quite significant. The remarks mentioned above enhance the findings of the interviews and also supports the suggestion that collaboration and sharing enhances creativity and alters the impression of the final product.

CONCLUSIONS

One of the main findings and suggestive arguments that came out from the in depth interviews, the intervention, and the interaction on the facebook page of the event is that collaboration within prosuming activities alters our mindset regarding the final product. Collaboration activities (both in the phase of production and in the phase of consumption) were found to enhance the enjoyment of the creation and alter the overall impression of the outcome. Moreover, prosumption within collaborative activities makes a shift on the acknowledged qualities of the resulting product.

NEW DIRECTIONS ON DESIGN

Therefore collaborative activities that enclose actions of prosumerism could focus more on the process of the creation and view the material object of the outcome under a different light. Under this light within the digital domain, participatory communities could enhance the process of collaborative creation and collaborative consumption, therefore *collaborative prosumption* and lead to differential approaches and interaction designs.

What could be the role of the unexpected in the design process? In this paper it is suggested that the unexpected enhances creativity and establishes new connections. William Mitchell in his essay "After the revolution_ Instruments of displacement" (in the book "Disappearing architecture") is referring to the significance of the unexpected in the phase of creation. Specifically he is talking about the immaterial

values of the spaces created especially now through the digital technology suggesting that the challenge is “to start thinking like creative fusion chefs – to create spaces that satisfy important human needs in effective new ways, and that surprise and delight us through digitally enabled combinations of the unexpected”.

THE DOUBLE FORM OF PROSUMPTION

What shows as most important in prosumerism and especially in the prosumerism of culinary activities is the double form of prosumption, both for self-use and pleasure and in the same time for establishing new ways of collaborations and creation. This remark within the realm of digital prosumerism and in addition to the view put forward by Hintikka Kari, (Hintikka, 2010) who is of the opinion that, in mass media and daily life, social media is considered suitable mostly for leisure and entertainment purposes could lead to new conditions. Social media tools could increasingly be adopted for new models of collaboration within organizations, project groups and professional networks in order to enhance collaboration within prosuming activities.

Specifically the suggestive conclusions that were reached are: 1. Collaboration and sharing within activities of prosumerism enhance creativity and alter the overall impression of the outcome. 2. Prosumption is related both to self-use and pleasure and to the

creation of innovative connections and the formation of new ways of collaborations. 3. In prosumption the creation of new customs and the promotion of new ideas are established through the unexpected.

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